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Review Article

**REVIEW OF REHABILITATION EFFICIENCY FOR
POLYMYOSITIS**¹Zahra Adel AlGhanim, ²Hassan Mohammed AlMadan, ³Raniah Riyadh Al Dhneem, ⁴Noor Baqir AlAwami, ⁵Fatima Baqir AlAwami**Abstract:**

In this review we discuss the background of the polymyositis, physical examination and treatment in rehabilitation phase. Medline and Embase Database were electronically searched through September 2018. polymyositis (PM) is an idiopathic inflammatory ailment of striated muscle mass, it takes place most frequently in women between the ages of 50 and 70. The predominant clinical indication is proximal muscle weakness. There might be extra muscle involvement such as inflammatory arthritis, Raynaud's phenomenon, myocarditis, and interstitial lung illness. Serum muscle enzymes are normally elevated during durations of active disease. A range of autoantibodies are often located in the serum of PM patients. Definitive diagnosis is established by muscle biopsy. Corticosteroids are the mainstay of treatment, but a variety of other immunomodulatory agents are made use of in the management of this illness. The majority of patients reply to treatment, although some degree of long-term muscle damages is not unusual.

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INTRODUCTION:

The idiopathic inflammatory myopathies (IIM) are a heterogeneous bunch of uncommon illness that primarily influence skeletal muscle mass. In grownups, IIMs are split into polymyositis (PM), dermatomyositis (DM) and inclusion body myositis (IBM), while children are primarily affected by juvenile dermatomyositis (JDM) although some are diagnosed with overlap juvenile idiopathic inflammatory myopathy [1]. The common characteristic of all patients with IIMs suffers muscle function, nonetheless each subgroup provides with characteristic muscle pathology and medical symptoms such as interstitial lung illness, fatigue and dysphagia.

Polymyositis is one of a group of muscle diseases referred to as the inflammatory myopathies, which are characterized by chronic muscle inflammation accompanied by muscle weakness. Polymyositis impacts skeletal muscles (those involved with making motion) on both sides of the body. It is rarely seen in individuals under age 18; most cases are in grownups among the ages of 31 and 60 [2]. Dynamic muscle group weakness starts in the proximal muscles (muscles closest to the trunk of the body) which ultimately leads to problems climbing upstairs, increasing from a seated position, lifting items, or getting to overhead. People with polymyositis may additionally experience arthritis, shortness of breath, trouble swallowing and talking, and heart arrhythmias. In many cases of polymyositis, distal muscles (muscles additionally away from the trunk of the body, such as those in the forearms and around the ankles and wrists) might be influenced as the ailment progresses. Polymyositis might be associated with collagen-vascular or autoimmune illness, such as lupus. Polymyositis might also be associated with contagious disorders, such as HIV-AIDS [2].

Physical exercise plays a crucial role in the therapy of inflammatory myopathies. In the phase of acute muscle mass inflammation, the prevention of contractures in the joints and physiotherapy for the respiratory system are the most essential aims, whereas in the healing phase of dermatomyositis and polymyositis the focus should be on the strengthening of remaining muscle fibers. In this review we discuss the background of the polymyositis, physical examination and treatment in rehabilitation phase.

METHODOLOGY:

Medline and Embase Database abstracts were electronically searched through September 2018 using the search terms myositis, polymyositis, and rehabilitation. All references list of included studies were manually searched for more relevant articles

We limited our review to only human subject's studies in English.

DISCUSSION:

- **Symptoms**

The initial symptoms are usually painless weakness of the pelvic and proximal lower extremity muscle mass, which can cause difficulty walking and climbing up stairways or in standing up after sitting in a chair. Commonly the next muscles influenced are those of the neck and shoulder girdle. The degree of weakness may differ from light to close to paralysis [2]. Weakness normally develops gradually over weeks to months, although in unusual instances weakness may advance more swiftly.

Other PM symptoms consist:

1. Difficulty swallowing (dysphasia)
2. Difficulty speaking
3. Arthralgia
4. Fatigue
5. Shortness of breath

The primary symptom of PM is muscle weakness. Weakness is symmetric, affecting the proximal muscles of the extremities as well as the neck flexors. Weakness of the distal muscles is unusual, and when existing need to necessitate factor to consider of another type of myopathy, such as inclusion body myositis. PM patients might occasionally experience pain and tenderness in the muscles, which can imitate the symptoms of polymyalgia rheumatica [2]. Participation of the striated muscle mass of the oropharynx and top esophagus takes place in 10-15% of patients, is a weak prognostic indicator, and might lead to dysphagia, regurgitation, and aspiration pneumonia. Interstitial lung ailment happens in 5-10% of patients. In addition, there may be ventilatory disorder because of involvement of the diaphragm and intercostal muscle groups. Cardiac involvement is frequently asymptomatic, however might lead to transmission disturbances, myocarditis, or heart disease. Raynaud's phenomenon, non-erosive arthritis, and systemic signs and symptoms of morning stiffness, fatigue, weight reduction, and fever all may be present during the course of PM. [1], [2]. Polymyositis is significantly being identified as a bucket term for IIMs that do not have the specific requirements for position into the other four subcategories or which are unfavorable for myositis-specific antibody. Patients typically provide in a way similar to dermatomyositis with subacute proximal symmetric muscle weakness; however, polymyositis patients are without characteristic rashes of dermatomyositis and have generated different results

relative to muscle histopathology, as demonstrated in Table 1. Lotion CK levels might be boosted

approximately 50 times the ceiling of normal in the subacute active stage [1], [3].

Table 1. Idiopathic inflammatory myopathies subcategories and classical muscle biopsy pathology findings . The presence of vacuoles are pathognomonic for inclusion body myositis [1],[3].

IIMs Sub-Category	Muscle Pathology	Vacuole Formation
Polymyositis	CD8 ⁺ T-cells; MHC-1 antigen expression	No
Dermatomyositis	Perivascular; perimysial; perifascicular inflammation; +/- necrotic fibers; perifascicular atrophy and decreased capillaries; macrophages, B-cells and CD4 ⁺ T-cells	No
Autoimmune necrotizing myositis	Necrotic fibers with macrophages; absence of CD8 ⁺ T-cells; complement deposition may be present	No
Sporadic inclusion body myositis	CD8 ⁺ T-cells; cytochrome-oxidase negative; congophilic amyloid deposits	Yes

Idiopathic inflammatory myositis (IIM); Major histocompatibility complex (MHC).

• Physical Examination

Symmetric weakness of the proximal muscles is the most consistent physical discovery in PM. Muscle mass tenderness may occasionally be present, however deep tendon reflexes are preserved. The sensory exam is normally regular. Muscle wasting or degeneration might be present in sophisticated situations. Exam of the lungs may expose dry inspiratory crackles. Dysphonia with a nasal speech top quality may be mentioned [4]. Precise manual muscle mass strength testing is seriously vital to do. The Medical Research Council's grading system for muscular tissue strength analysis is widely used.

Strength is graded according to the following scale:

Grade 0=No discernible muscle contraction.

Grade 1=Muscle contraction visible but no limb movement possible.

Grade 2=Movement of limb possible with gravity eliminated.

Grade 3=Movement against gravity only without additional resistance.

Grade 4=Movement against some resistance.

Grade 5=Normal strength against resistance.

Other physical findings might include joint tenderness and/or swelling, rash, and subcutaneous nodules [4].

• Treatment

There is no cure for polymyositis, however the symptoms can be treated. Choices consist of medication, physical and occupational therapy, exercise, heat treatment (consisting of microwave and ultrasound), orthotics and assistive gadgets, and remainder. The conventional treatment for polymyositis is a corticosteroid drug, provided either in pill form or intravenously. Immunosuppressant drugs, such as azathioprine and methotrexate, may

lower inflammation in individuals that do not respond well to prednisone [5]. Routine therapy utilizing intravenous immunoglobulin can additionally boost recuperation. Various immunosuppressive agents used to treat the inflammation connected with polymyositis include cyclosporine A, cyclophosphamide, and tacrolimus. Physical treatment is usually advised to stop muscle degeneration and to gain back muscle mass stamina and range of activity. Occupational therapists can prepare an analysis of everyday activities to aid address concerns such as bathing and consuming.

Physical Therapy in the Rehabilitation

Routine physical activity and exercise lead to favorable wellness outcomes such as enhanced neuromuscular adjustment, boosted muscular tissue function, and reduced threat of osteoporosis. Cardiovascular exercise also lowers the danger of heart disease. The American College of Sports Medicine has actually released general recommendations for physical activity and exercise (Table 2) [6], [7]. Due to the fact that patients with rheumatic illness are at raised risk for heart disease, regular exercise is very important in their treatment to reduce disability, to reduce morbidity in cardiovascular disease, and to improve function [8]. Till recently, nevertheless, patients with inflammatory myopathies were urged to avoid physical activity and exercise because of concern that workout would certainly worsen muscle swelling. In 1993 the first case records of the safety and helpful effects of workout were reported in patients with polymyositis and dermatomyositis [9], [10]. Since 1993 a few more records have been released on workout in patients with inflammatory myopathies.

Table 2. The American College of Sports Medicine recommendations for physical activity and exercise [6],[7] .

<p>Physical activity for health benefits Purpose: establish a habit of regular physical activity to promote health Mode: aerobic activity Frequency: most days of the week Intensity: 40—60% max VO₂ = 60—80% MHR = RPE = 3—4 (light and moderate activities) Duration: 30 minutes accumulation of moderate activity during the day</p>
<p>Exercise Training for Physical Fitness Purpose: Increase cardiovascular and muscular through regular physiologic overload</p>
<p>Exercise training for cardiovascular fitness Mode: Aerobic activity Frequency: 3—5 days/week Intensity: 50—70% max VO₂ = 60—80% MHR = RPE = 3—6 (moderate to vigorous activities) Duration: 20—60 minutes continuous</p>
<p>Exercise training for muscular fitness (strength and endurance) Mode: Resistance exercise (free weights, machines, elastic bands) Frequency: 2—3 days/week Volume: 8—10 exercises; 8—12 lifts of a load that can be lifted correctly and produce local fatigue in 8—12 repetitions; 1—3 sets as tolerated</p>

RPE, rating of perceived exertion (0—10); MHR, age-predicted maximal heart rate $220 - \text{age}$; max VO₂, maximal oxygen uptake.

The very first two case reports released in 1993 used short-term exercise durations in six patients with both chronic and active polymyositis and dermatomyositis. One study reported boosted muscle mass toughness after a 6-week isometric toughness training program by use of a Cybex tool [10]. The other situation record consisted of five patients with active disease that took part in alternating 2-week periods of submaximal muscle training and more easy range-of-motion workout programs. Safety and security and benefits were assessed individually for every patient. Growths in peak isometric stamina and decrease of action limitation throughout periods of active exercise differed from 22 to 40% and from 4 to 42%, respectively [9]. Both studies reported unchanged s-CK degrees after the exercise periods. A discrepancy exists among s-CK levels and degree of inflammatory infiltrates and muscle mass problems [11], [12]. Consequently, Alexanderson et al. operated a much more mindful approach to evaluate muscle mass swelling [13]. The researchers incorporated muscle group biopsies, MRI, and s-CK degrees to assess muscle mass inflammation after a 12-week home exercise program. This open research study was executed in 10 patients with chronic polymyositis or dermatomyositis. Patients executed an easy to moderate repellent 20- minute home workout program in addition to a 15-minute walk five days a week during 12 weeks. There were no indicators of boosted muscle inflammation according to analysis of muscle biopsy specimens, MRI, or s-CK levels, and the team improved considerably by 15 to 17% lowered impairment, examined by the FI, and 23% lowered activity limitation/participation

restriction (SF-36) (Table 3) [13]. This home workout program was additionally reviewed in 11 patients with recent-onset active polymyositis and dermatomyositis [14]. Ten patients had indicators of active muscle inflammation in evaluation of muscle biopsy specimens, MRI, or s-CK degrees before starting the workout program. After 12 weeks of workout there were no indications of increased swelling, and the group enhanced considerably, with 12 to 16% lowered disability and 25 to 45% minimized task limitation/participation limitation (Table 3) [14]. Twenty-two patients with polymyositis or dermatomyositis and 3 patients with addition body myositis, in all stages of their illness, took part in a 3-week exercise and patient curriculum [15]. The patients subjectively reported joining either specific physical treatment oversaw exercise, group acrobatics in a keep-fit club or in a pool, pain-revealing treatment, or exterior walking. General s-CK degrees remained unmodified, and the team boosted considerably by a mean 4% decreased disability assessed by the FI. Another research evaluated a 3-week submaximal muscle endurance program along with medical spa therapies in 9 patients with chronic disease and 10 patients with active muscle mass inflammation [16]. Both teams enhanced considerably in isometric muscle mass toughness, with mean 37% and 46% increase in the active team and chronic team, respectively. Renovation in tiredness and aerobic fitness was also reported, and s-CK levels remained unchanged in both teams [16]. We performed an extensive 7-week muscular training program in patients with chronic steady polymyositis or dermatomyositis. The

program consisted of resistive exercise in five muscle mass groups on the load of 10 voluntary repeating maximum (VRM) done in three sets. This resulted in significantly minimized impairment, boosted muscle mass toughness (10- 15 VRM), and enhanced endurance (FI-2) without signs of enhanced muscle mass swelling gauged by the medical professional's global analysis of condition activity, muscle biopsies, or s-CK degrees.

A small randomized regulated test reported enhanced ultimate oxygen uptake and isometric muscle strength after a 60-minute cardio biking and step-up exercise program on 60 to 70% of maximal heart rate compared to an inactive control group after both 6 weeks and 6 months [17], [18].

Table 3. Overview of published studies evaluating safety and benefits of different exercise regimens in patients with idiopathic inflammatory myopathies

Regimen	Study and design	Patients (n)	Diagnosis	Disease activity	Training duration	Load/intensity (% of max)	Outcome safety	Outcome benefits	Results
1. Muscular training	Hicks JE et al. [10]	1	PM	Chronic	6 wk	60%	s-CK	Isometric peak torque	+
	Escalante A et al. [9]	5	PM/DM	Active	8 wk	NR	s-CK	Isometric peak torque, modified HAQ	+
	Alexanders on et al. [13]	10	PM/DM	Chronic	12 wk	NR	Muscle biopsy, MRI, s-CK	Muscle endurance, (FI), SF-36	+
	Alexanders on et al. [14]	11	PM/DM	Active	12 wk	NR	Muscle biopsy, MRI, s-CK	Muscle endurance, (FI), SF-36	+
	Heikkilä et al. [15]	22	PM/DM / IBM	Chronic/active	3 wk	NR	s-CK, pain	Muscle endurance, (FI)	+
	Varjú et al. [16]	19	PM/DM	Chronic/active	3 wk	NR	s-CK, pain, fatigue	Isometric peak torque, HAQ	+
2. Aerobic exercise	Wiesinger et al. [17]	14	PM/DM	Chronic	6 wk	70%	s-CK	VO ₂ max, Isometric peak torque, HAQ	+
	Wiesinger et al. [18]	13	PM/DM	Chronic	6 mo	70%	s-CK	VO ₂ max, Isometric peak torque, HAQ	+

PM, polymyositis; DM, dermatomyositis; VRM, voluntary repetition maximum; s-CK, serum creatine kinase; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; FI, functional index in myositis; VO₂ max, maximal oxygen uptake; Short Form Health Survey (SF-36); NR, not reported.

- **Prognosis**

The prognosis for polymyositis varies. Most individuals respond fairly well to treatment, however some have an extra severe illness that does not respond adequately to therapies and are left with significant ailment. In uncommon situations individuals with extreme and progressive muscle weakness will develop breathing failure or pneumonia. Problem swallowing may create weight loss and malnutrition. The cause of death in PM adjustments with disease duration. Pulmonary problems are a regular cause of death within the initial 12 months of illness, whereas cardiac complications are an even more usual cause of death 5 years after PM/DM is identified [19]. About 20% of corticosteroid-treated PM patients will attain remission and be off all treatment within a 5-year follow-up duration, whereas 80% will certainly have a chronic, continual disease program requiring recurring immunosuppressive therapy [22]. It is essential to be aware of the many prognostic factors for PM to assist guide care. Age is the most vital predictor of death in PM, as patients > 64 years old demonstrate a death rate of 47.8% compared to 9.1% in younger patients [23]. Male gender, non-Caucasian race, cancer, esophageal participation, breathing participation, and cardiac disorder, are forecasters of poor prognosis in PM [19], [20], [21].

CONCLUSION:

PM is an idiopathic inflammatory ailment of striated muscle mass. The illness takes place most frequently in women between the ages of 50 and 70. The predominant clinical indication is proximal muscle weakness. There might be extra muscle involvement such as inflammatory arthritis, Raynaud's phenomenon, myocarditis, and interstitial lung illness. Serum muscle enzymes are normally elevated during durations of active disease. A range of autoantibodies are often located in the serum of PM patients. Characteristic abnormalities are frequently seen on EMG and muscle mass MRI. Definitive diagnosis is established by muscle biopsy. Corticosteroids are the mainstay of treatment, but a variety of other immunomodulatory agents are made use of in the management of this illness. The majority of patients reply to treatment, although some degree of long-term muscle damages is not unusual.

Although published studies examining exercise treatment in patients with inflammatory myopathies are not many and include small example sizes, they still sustain the notion that workout can be used without raised muscle swelling. Additionally, enhanced muscle function and cardiovascular ability can be attained with exercise. Thus, active workout

adjusted to disease task and handicap might be advised in the rehabilitation of patients with chronic along with inflammatory active PM. Additional research study is required in the form of multicenter randomized controlled tests to develop the efficacy of different exercise regimens.

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